

REPRESENTATION OF EMOTIONS IN UZBEK LINGUOCULTURE

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Annotation: This article describes the situations in which emotions are expressed in Uzbek culture, and they are revealed with Uzbek proverbs and expressions and their translation into English.

Key words: emotion, shame, culture, mentality, peculiarity, guilt, body language, gestures, posture, facial structure, happiness, hatred, disgust, sadness, expression

We have analyzed linguacultural concepts of words which defines emotional states like “happiness” (baxt), “sorrow”(g'am), “anger” (jahl), “disgust” (jirkanish), “satisfaction” (qoniqish) in Uzbek language. These concepts are considered from the standpoint of comparative linguistics and translation studies in terms of the analysis of lexical and phraseological fields of these concepts. Humankind builds his own world on the basis of these ideas of emotions. People can not live without making any judgments about these concepts. “Understanding variability in emotion perception is only emerging, and the neural basis of any impact from the structure of emotion-concept knowledge remains unknown. In a neuroimaging study, we used a representational similarity analysis (RSA) approach to measure the correspondence between the conceptual, perceptual, and neural representational structures of the six emotion categories Anger, Disgust, Fear, Happiness, Sadness, and Surprise.”

“Thereafter, the word “happiness” (baxt) sounds different in different languages; in each language has its synonym field. The study of verbalization of the concept of “happiness” (baxt) in both English and Uzbek pictures of the world led to the conclusion that in the perception of this concept there are both general and specific aspects, which enables us to consider this concept has universal and national-specific mental structures. Concept of “happiness / baxt” refers to a person's feelings and reflects satisfaction, so you can understand that feeling “happiness / baxt” associated with emotions close to joy, considering sense of joy in the background.” We will look into the details of every emotions we have said before. We will begin with the emotion “happiness”.

In Uzbek language “happiness / baxt” show significant positive moments. The Uzbek etymological dictionary gives “baxt” as persian derivation. An analysis of the etymological dictionaries show us that concept of “baxt” has semantic and linguacultural aspects. “Conceptual structure also predicts multiple behavioral patterns of emotion perception, including cross-cultural differences in patterns of emotion categorizations. These findings suggest that emotion perception, and the brain's representations of face categories, can be flexibly influenced by conceptual understanding of emotions.” In Uzbek language there are synonyms can be given as an example: saodat, omad, shodlik, xursandchilik, iqbol, masud, rohat, farog'at, mamnunlik. The analysis show that synonymous in the ranks of the concept “Happiness / Baxt” observed semantical correlative pairs: – glad — mamnunlik (Rejoice) – fortunate — iqbol, omad (good luck) – contentment rohat, farog'at (satisfaction). The concept

“happiness” shows fortune (luck) and satisfaction (contentment). In Uzbek language there are idioms which includes the concept happiness: –

1. Ishning omadi — oz vaqti bor. (Lucky thing has its time.)
2. Omad kelsa sichqon filni yengar. (If luck comes, mouse win an elephant.)
3. Rohat mehnatning orqasida. (Happiness comes by making effort.)
4. Halol mehnat — yahshi odat, berur senga saodat. (Honest work will lead to happiness.)
5. Mehnat -farogat chirog'i. (Labor — it is the light of happiness.)

“As the analysis of the linguistic material, “Happiness” in both languages considered the positive emotions and is positive evaluation. However, in Uzbek language it has seeing negative connotation. For example, saying “Birovning baxti, birovning ko'zini chiqaribdi” which translates as (someone else's happiness, another man's unhappiness) denotes that not everyone can rejoice in another's happiness.” The concept of “Happiness” has metaphorical units in Uzbek language: – Happiness — Poultry: Baxt qushi boshiga qo'ndi (bird of happiness on his head). – Happiness — subject: Baxtin sinamoq (Experience happiness), Baxtin bermok (give happiness). – Happiness — a living organism: Baxti kulgan (Smiling happiness) Baxti ochilgan (lucky person) omad kelgan (luck has come). Thus, in the Uzbek language the description of the female has a positive emotion which shows the value of her internal soul qualities, the priority of family relationship: – yaxshi xotin oilaning davlati va baxti (a good wife is the happiness of the family) – xotin baxti — erda bo'lar (the happiness of the wife depends on her husband). The concept of happiness in Uzbek language connected with a girl or woman. There are some more examples concerning this point: –

1. Bolani baxtini bersin / baxti ochilsin. (Let the girl be happy.)
2. Xon taxtidan qo'rqar, qiz — baxtidan. (The king is afraid of losing his throne and the girl by her own happiness.)
3. Qizga oltin taxt emas, barmoqday baxt tila. (Do not wish a golden throne for a girl, but better happiness.)
4. Qizning baxti- urning davlati. (Woman's happiness — the wealth of the husband.)
5. Har narsaning vaqti bor, har bir qizning baxti bor. (There is a certain time for everything as every girl has her own happiness.)

In this context, the happiness of a girl or a woman is perceived as a successful marriage. By the same time there is something said about men:

6. Har yigitga bir omad. (Every man has one luck.)
7. Yigit boshidan davlat yiroq ketmas. (Happiness and wealth will not go far away from the man), there is a man's happiness seen in a big fortune and wealth. Since ancient times, the Uzbek save and hide their most valuable items in some accessible place as a chest which gives a clear conclusion that happiness for the Uzbek nation important and valuable.

In terms of “sorrow” (g'am), it was taken from Arabic word “gammun” it means someone or something make somebody upset. It has its own synonyms like (qayg'u, ruhiy azob) in Uzbek sometimes it is used to make compound words like “g'am-g'ussa” and “g'am-hasrat”. It has its adjective form “g'amgin” which means sad or upset. There are some proverbs which defines the sorrow from different perspectives:

1. Dard tomirni yer, hasrat umrni. (Sorrow can eat the life of a man.)
2. Devorni nam yiqitar, odamni g'am. (Sorrow can be the very reason of being unsuccessful.)

3. Joni borning g'ami bor. (Here sorrow is described as the trait that every person had in their life. No one is exception.)
4. Moli ko'pning g'ami ko'p. (Sometimes I have a lot (being rich) can make your life miserable.)
5. O'ylasang qayg'u ko'p, o'ylamasang qayg'u yo'q. (If you want to find a problem, you will find it, so don't search.)
6. O'tda yongan kuyar, g'amda yongan o'lar. (Flames can burn your flesh but sorrow can burn your soul.)
7. Har kechaning kunduzi, har kunduzning kechasi. (There is an end in every miserable situation.)

Linguacultural aspects of this emotion indicates to negative connotation of the word, it describes the situation which one can come across when they are in their dark times, for example when they fail, lose the close ones, be betrayed and do something bad for their psychology. In Uzbek culture usually it is identified in the funeral when one lose their loved ones.

There are some idioms which the emotion of "sorrow" is described:

1. Boshiga kulfat tushdi – someone has a problem which can cause sadness
2. Qora kunlar – the days that one can feel sorrow
3. Tashvishi aridi – sorrowful days have come to an end
4. G'amdan ado bo'ldi- becoming burnt down by sorrow

If it comes to the emotion of "anger", this word comes from Arabic language "jahln" and it means "being stupid" in Arabic language, but in Uzbek it means "becoming angry". There is a verb form of that word- "jahllanmoq" and the adjective form is "jahldor" and it means "angry". In addition to that, there some synonyms in Uzbek language: achchig'i chiqmoq, jahldan qizil bo'lib ketmoq, jahlini sochmoq, g'azablanmoq and others.

There are some proverbs which can reflect anger from linguacultural perspective.

1. Jahl chiqsa aql ketadi. (When someone is angry, they can lose their mind.)
2. Achchig'ing kelsa burningni tishla. (It is your doing that you are angry.)
3. Bugungi jahlni ertaga qo'yma. (If you want to be angry, be angry today)
4. Jahl-joningga jabr. (Angriness can cause damage to health.)
5. Jahlning dushmani sabr. (Patience is the enemy of angriness.)
6. Jahl bilan qilingan ish boshga keltirar tashvish. (When somebody is angry, they have a high chance of making a mistake.)

"Hate is based on perceptions of a stable, negative disposition of persons or groups. We hate persons and groups more because of who they are, than because of what they do. Hate has the goal to eliminate its target. Hate is especially significant at the intergroup level, where it turns already devalued groups into victims of hate. When shared among group members, hate can spread fast in conflict zones where people are exposed to hate-based violence, which further feeds their hate. Hate can be reassuring and self-protective, because its message is simple and helps confirming people's belief in a just world." In Uzbek linguaculture angriness is depicted as negative emotion which can lead to the harm for life. That's why Uzbek people don't like to be angry, even if they are angry, they try to be calm. Uzbek language is rich in such extravagant idioms that every idiom is suitable for its exact situation. There are some idioms which can depict the meaning of being angry:

1. Jahl otiga minmoq (to go ballistic)
2. G'azabini sochmoq (steam pour out of somebody's eyes)
3. Zahrini sochmoq (to be in a rage)
4. Jahldan sholg'omdek bo'lib ketmoq (see red)

If it comes to "satisfaction" (qoniqish), Uzbek people love expressing their satisfaction by praising and giving traits. They usually say "thank you" (rahmat), "god bless you" (olloh rozi bo'lsin), "karma is real, wait till it comes" (mendan qaytmasa xudodan qaytsin) when they are satisfied. In addition to that they usually give presents or pay for them when they feel to make satisfied. Even education grading system includes marks which depicts this emotion: "satisfactory" (qoniqarli) and "unsatisfactory" (qoniqarsiz). Uzbeks feel powerful and grateful when they have something as they wish.

However, the feeling of "disgust" (jirkanish) is one of the negative ones that can effect state of person in every culture. Its synonyms are "nafratlanish, g'azablanish, norozi bo'lish". In Uzbek culture, "disgust" (jirkanish) is usually expressed by facial expressions like grinned smile, grounded face and tremble in body. They usually become disgusted by the dirty things, like meals, food, clothes, people or situations. When they feel disgusted about something, they usually don't feel like use these things again, like they are completely don't feel like to have them again in their life like they quit. There are some idioms which includes "disgust" (jirkanish):

1. Muhabbat ketsa, nafrat kelar, nafrat kelsa, muhabbat ketar. (The greatest hate springs from the greatest love.)
2. Muhabbat va nafratning orasi bir qadam. (There is a very small distance between love and hate.)
3. Ovqatdan jirkangan och qolar. (The one who feels disgust about food will be hungry eventually.)
4. Kimdan jirkansa, bolasi shunga o'xshar. (There is a high chance for the children of looking similar to the person the one feels disgusted about.)

Also, from the ancient times the people of Uzbekistan demonstrate their disgust with exclamations. For example: viy, voy, voyey, blaq, pfu and others. All in all, these emotions are very vital in every linguaculture as well as Uzbek.

As human beings, we experience sensations that vary in degree or perception. Nevertheless, we could be unaware of those feelings or how to interpret them. This is largely because some feelings are hard to observe and interpret. However, emotions affect the way we think much as they may not be perceived to directly influence behavior and the way we act towards others. Among the major basic emotions according to him are happiness, confidence or trust, fear, wonder or astonishment, sadness, repugnance, ire and expectancy. These emotions coexist in opposites. Feelings like love, disappointment, aggressiveness, guilt, optimism, contempt, awe, remorse and their opposites arise from the basic emotions.

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